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On Graph Deep Learning for Time Series Forecasting

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In modern cyber-physical systems, physical and virtual sensors continuously produce large amounts of data. Such pervasive sensor networks acquire partial heterogeneous observations at different rates and scales. The result is large collections of correlated, heterogeneous and irregular time series that learning systems should continuously integrate and process to make accurate predictions. Leveraging and modelling the spatiotemporal structure of the data is crucial to building models that can scale. Deep learning models have become fundamental tools in modern forecasting practice. The most successful approach consists of training a single deep network on collections of related time series while sharing parameters. Although this allows for training large (*global*) models on vast amounts of data, the resulting predictors process a time series at a time: they cannot leverage existing relationships among time series. My dissertation, *Graph Deep Learning for Time Series Forecasting*, shows that graph deep learning (GDL) provides the appropriate framework and inductive biases to go beyond the limitations of the current state of the art in deep learning for time series forecasting. Within the proposed framework, dependencies are modelled in terms of pairwise relationships among time series in the collection. The resulting representation is a graph where each time series is associated with a node, and functional relationships among them are represented as edges.

Graph deep learning for time series forecasting

The thesis's **goal** is the introduction of a comprehensive methodological framework

instrumental to designing GDL methods for time series forecasting, providing the necessary tools and theory. In particular, we introduced novel methods and techniques to build, understand and scale graph-based predictors, i.e. methods to process and forecast collections of correlated time series given graph-based input representations [Cini et al., 2025]. The thesis provides a formalisation of the problem settings, representations and predictors. Available design choices and their implications are discussed, together with guidelines and methodologies to address associated challenges. Results show that graph-based processing allows for building scalable predictors while taking structural dependencies among time series into account. A schematic outline of the project, its goal and challenges is provided in Figure 1. The following provides more details on the challenges we dealt with and our contribution in addressing them.

Challenge 1: Local effects.

Time series might be heterogeneous and characterised by specific dynamics (*local effects*). Specialising forecasting models to such dynamics can hinder transferability and scalability. We developed methodologies to address local effects by developing graph-based forecasting architectures with shared components and local processing blocks [Cini et al., 2023b]. Local components, i.e. modules with node-specific parameters, allow for tailoring the processing to the characteristics of each input time series. This research line addressed the implications of introducing such components in transductive and transfer learning scenarios and discussed the associated trade-offs.

Challenge 2: Missing data.

Missing data and intermittent observations (across both time and space) are inherent to any application involving a network of sensors. This makes the processing challenging, particularly in those applications characterised by extremely sparse observations. Within the thesis, we pioneered several state-of-the-art GDL methodologies for missing data imputation in collections of irregular time series and spatiotemporal data. The introduced methods rely

on relational representations to reconstruct missing data by leveraging observations at the target time series and neighbouring nodes [Cini et al., 2022; Marisca et al., 2022]. This work opened up a line of research—graph-based neural imputation—which is currently very active and represents the state of the art in several applications. In this context, we also explored applications of this approach to the virtual sensing problem [Cini et al., 2022; De Felice et al., 2024], i.e. to the problem of reconstructing observations at locations where no physical sensor is available.

Figure 1: Outline of the nominee's dissertation highlighting the research goal and related challenges.

Challenge 3: Latent graph learning.

Available relational information can be inaccurate, inadequate, or completely missing. Exploiting relational architectures in such a setting requires extracting relationships from data. To address this challenge, the thesis studied the problem of learning latent graph structures directly from time series in an end-to-end fashion (**Challenge 3**) [Cini et al., 2023c]. Specifically, the thesis introduces methodologies for learning distributions over graphs while maintaining sparsity and computational efficiency in downstream graph-based processing. This was achieved by proposing novel variance-reduced score-based gradient estimators. The resulting graph learning framework also enabled the development of state-space models in which inputs, outputs and states are all represented as graphs [Zambon et al., 2023].

Challenge 4: Scalability.

In real-world applications, processing observations over both time and space has a high

computational cost. Effectively exploiting the available spatiotemporal dependencies can then be extremely challenging and requires ad-hoc scalable operators. In the thesis, we propose scalable forecasting architectures by combining graph processing and deep randomised recurrent neural networks [Cini et al., 2023a]. The introduced architectures extract spatiotemporal representations without requiring any training; representations can be precomputed and then mapped to predictions by a decoder, which is the only trainable component of the architecture. Precomputation makes the cost of a training step independent of graph size and sequence length. The associated paper won the Best Paper Award at the Temporal Graph Learning workshop at NeurIPS 2022, one of the most prominent workshops in learning from dynamic relational data.

Future directions

Besides addressing the identified challenges, we also investigated graph-based models operating at adaptive spatial resolution. In particular, the thesis introduces a methodology unifying graph-based forecasting with hierarchical time series processing. The resulting framework enables the modelling of higher-order spatiotemporal structures. I am currently following up on this work funded by a Swiss National Science Foundation Postdoc Fellowship at the University of Oxford.

Dissemination, impact and applications

Most of the methodologies designed within the thesis have been published together with open-

[i https://torch-spatiotemporal.readthedocs.io/en/latest/](https://torch-spatiotemporal.readthedocs.io/en/latest/)

source implementations. Furthermore, we developed and open-sourced *Torch Spatiotemporal*ⁱ, a software library for prototyping spatiotemporal graph neural networks and processing time series collections. The methods developed in the thesis have found several practical real-world applications, e.g. in smart grid and load forecasting applications, in collaboration with Siemens (Zurich) and DXT Commodities (Lugano). More recently, we applied the graph-based imputation approaches to process biomedical signals and, in particular, to reconstruct atrial fibrillation dynamics in collaboration with Imperial College London.

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